

Supplementary Material 2

References for adding within-genus branching to supertree phylogeny

Details for each species in accompanying excel sheet ‘species_tree_refs’.

Acinetobacter^{1,2}
Aeromonas³
Bacillus^{4,5}
Burkholderia⁶
Campylobacter⁷
Chlamydia⁸
Clostridium⁹
Enterobacter¹⁰
Enterococcus¹¹
Escherichia¹²
Klebsiella¹³
Lacticaseibacillus¹⁴
Latilactobacillus¹⁴
Lactiplantibacillus¹⁴
Levilactobacillus¹⁴
Ligilactobacillus¹⁴
Limosilactobacillus¹⁴
Mycobacterium¹⁵
Priestia¹⁶
Pseudomonas¹⁷
Pseudosulfitobacter^{18,19}
Rhodococcus²⁰
Shigella²¹
Staphylococcus^{22,23}
Vibrio²⁴
Xanthomonas²⁵
Yersinia²⁶

References

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